

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“RUDDY GLOW BUDDY”

An amazing heart and mind;
Knowing someone who's humane,
Not boastful in everything she claims;
Never speak hurtful words with a bad tone,
Full of respect to people, she's one of a kind;
Blessed in return with her compassion.

A gal stays miles away;
Desired to forget all the scary days,
Found someone, her love;
Her hope as it seems, in the land of dreams,
It's called "the City of Angels;"
A place of bangles and dangles,
Settles in permanently with a plan;
Thrive ahead, succeed, and lead to the land.

Seen her with great potential;
She is intellectual,
I mean this lady;
A real ruddy glow buddy.